

CLINICAL SIGNS OF CHILDREN'S CEREBRAL PALSY.**Yoldoshev Yorqinjon**

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Abstract This scientific article provides information clinical symptoms of cerebral palsy in children. As a material, the data of patients who underwent treatment in the private clinic of psychoneurological diseases of Fergana city during the years 2018-2023 were taken. It became known that the average number of people infected with CP in the world is 10%. It has been determined that the causes are polyetiological, the pathogenesis of which is the damage of the fetus during the intranatal period by the mother, intranatal hypoxia and infection. Clinical forms of CP each have their own specific symptoms.

Key words: children's cerebral palsy , epidemiology, etiology, pathogenesis, forms, clinic.

Main part.

Spastic diplegia G80.1 is the most common form and is known as Little's disease. A characteristic feature of the form of spastic diplegia is bilateral damage, deformation and contracture of the limbs. Additional symptoms of this disease include mental and language delay, pseudobulbar syndrome, cranial nerves pathology, optic disc atrophy, dysarthria, hearing impairment, and intellectual disability. Spastic diplegia is often observed in premature children, and specific changes in the brain are detected on MRI (6, 9, 20).

Spastic tetraparesis (bilateral hemiplegia) G80. 0 is considered one of the most severe forms and develops a severe anomaly in the brain. Homilaichi is manifested by diffuse damage of the brain tissue due to infection and perinatal hypoxia, often with the development of secondary microcephaly. Clinically, a bilateral spastic condition, that is, spastic changes are developed in both legs and arms to the same extent, only in some cases it is observed that the arms predominate. In this form, a wide range of accompanying symptoms are identified, including: cosoglasia, optic nerve atrophy, hearing impairment, pseudobulbar syndrome, severe language impairment, development of orthopedic complications, namely joint contracture and bone deformation (12, 21).

Unilateral spastic CP G 80.2 is often described by the development of unilateral spastic hemiparesis. It is observed that the hands are affected more strongly than the legs. In some cases, spastic monoparesis is detected.

Sometimes focal epileptic seizures may develop. The reason for this is a unilateral hemorrhagic stroke or a congenital anomaly of brain development is found. In this case, children with hemiparesis start making movements later than healthy children. Therefore, it is correct to take intellectual characteristics into account in such sick children, not movement (22).

CP dyskinetic form G80.3 – hyperkinesia in the form of involuntary movements, athetosis, choreoathetosis, dystonia in this form; change in muscle tone - may increase or decrease; manifested by speech disorders in the form of hyperkinetic dysarthria. Violation of the correct grip of the body and limbs. In most children, preservation of intellectual activity is observed, and changes in emotional activity are manifested by strength. One of the main causes of this form is hemolytic disease of babies, as well as damage to the basal nuclei as a result of intranatal asphyxia. In this case, the extrapyramidal system and the auditory cortex are usually damaged, and athetoid and dystonic variants are distinguished (23).

CP ataxic form G80.4 - this form is manifested by low muscle tone, ataxia, and increased sphincter reflexes. In this form, speech disorders are noted in the forms of cerebral and pseudobulbar dysarthria. Violation of body coordination is manifested by the appearance of tremors and dysmetria. In most cases of this form, disorders of the cerebrum, forehead-pons-cerebral pathway, damage to the forehead due to birth trauma, damage caused by hypoxia-ischemic factors, and the development of congenital anomalies are observed. This form should be carefully differentially diagnosed with hereditary diseases.

Conclusions

According to WHO data, the incidence rate of children's cerebral palsy is 2.5-3.3 per 1000 children, most of them are spastic, 82% of boys and 72% of girls.

The causes of CP are polyetiological, and the main ones are maternal pathologies and environmental influences in the prenatal and perinatal period, and the impact of these factors on the periventricular area and cortex of the brain leads to their damage and atrophy.

Clinically, there are several forms, including the most common spastic diplegia G80.1, the most severe form spastic tetraparesis G80.0, relatively mild forms: unilateral spastic CP G80.2, dyskinetic form G80.3, ataxic form G80.4 are distinguished

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